

THE SYSTEM OF SYMBOLIC IMAGES IN THE POETICS OF ALEXANDER FEINBERG

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada Aleksandr Faynberg poetikasida ramziy obrazlar tizimi tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqot davomida shoir she'riyatida qo'llangan ramzlarning badiiy vazifasi, ularning g'oyaviy-ma'naviy mazmunni ochishdagi o'rni hamda poetik tafakkur bilan bog'liqligi yoritiladi. Shuningdek, Faynberg lirikasida vaqt, yo'l, tun, yorug'lik kabi ramziy obrazlar orqali inson ruhiyati va hayot falsafasi ifodalanishi ilmiy jihatdan asoslab beriladi.

Kalit so'zlar. Aleksandr Faynberg, poetika, ramziy obraz, ramz, badiiy tasvir vositalari, lirika, falsafiy tafakkur, poetik obraz.

Annotation. This article analyzes the system of symbolic images in the poetics of Alexander Feinberg. The study sheds light on the artistic function of the symbols used in the poet's poetry, their role in revealing the ideological and spiritual content, and their connection with poetic thought. It also scientifically substantiates the expression of the human psyche and philosophy of life through symbolic images such as time, road, night, and light in Feinberg's lyrics.

Keywords. Alexander Feinberg, poetics, symbolic image, symbol, means of artistic expression, lyrics, philosophical thought, poetic image.

Аннотация. В данной статье анализируется система символических образов в поэтике Александра Файнберга. Исследование освещает художественную функцию символов, используемых в поэзии поэта, их роль в раскрытии идеологического и духовного содержания, а также их связь с поэтической мыслью. Также научно обосновывается выражение человеческой

психики и философии жизни через символические образы, такие как время, дорога, ночь и свет, в лирике Файнберга.

Ключевые слова: Александр Файнберг, поэтика, символический образ, символ, средства художественного выражения, лирика, философская мысль, поэтический образ.

Introduction. Symbols and symbolic images are one of the important artistic means in literature. Through symbols, a poet or writer expresses his idea not directly, but figuratively. This increases the artistic impact of the work and deepens its content. Alexander Feinberg's poetry is also distinguished by its richness in symbolic images. In his works, the poet expresses human life, spiritual experiences, and philosophy of life through various symbols. Therefore, studying the system of symbolic images in Feinberg's poetics is important from the point of view of literary criticism.

In Feinberg's poetry, symbolic images often serve to give a deeper understanding of life reality. The poet seeks to express the complex aspects of human life through various images. For example, the image of the road is often interpreted as a symbol of human life. This image depicts a person's life path, his quest and destiny. The image of night can also appear as a symbol expressing a person's inner experiences or mental state. The images of time and light also have an important symbolic meaning in Alexander Feinberg's poetics. Time is often used to express ideas such as the transience of human life and the shortness of life. The image of light is often interpreted as a symbol of hope, goodness or spiritual purity. Through these images, the poet shows, along with the complexity of life, the feelings of goodness and hope in the human heart. The symbols in Feinberg's poetry not only serve as artistic decoration, but also express deep philosophical content. The poet observes human life, his dreams, aspirations, and spiritual quests through symbolic images. As a result, the system of symbols in the poet's lyrics creates a holistic poetic structure. Through this system, the reader has the opportunity to understand the content of the poem more deeply.

In conclusion, the system of symbolic images in the poetics of Alexander Feinberg is one of the important artistic features. Through the use of symbols, the poet enhances the artistic expressiveness of his works and expresses a deep philosophical content. Feinberg's poetry artistically illuminates human life, spiritual experiences and spiritual values through symbolic images. Therefore, his poetics is a vivid example of symbolic thinking in modern poetry.

Kirish. Adabiyotda ramz va ramziy obrazlar muhim badiiy vositalardan biri hisoblanadi. Ramz orqali shoir yoki yozuvchi o'z fikrini bevosita emas, balki majoziy

yo‘l bilan ifodalaydi. Bu esa asarning badiiy ta‘sirchanligini oshirib, uning mazmunini yanada chuqurlashtiradi. Aleksandr Faynberg she‘riyati ham ramziy obrazlarga boyligi bilan ajralib turadi. Shoir o‘z asarlarida turli ramzlar orqali inson hayoti, ruhiy kechinmalar va hayot falsafasini ifodalaydi. Shu sababli Faynberg poetikasida ramziy obrazlar tizimini o‘rganish adabiyotshunoslik nuqtayi nazaridan muhim ahamiyatga ega.

Faynberg she‘riyatida ramziy obrazlar ko‘pincha hayotiy voqelikni chuqurroq anglatishga xizmat qiladi. Shoir turli obrazlar orqali inson hayotining murakkab jihatlarini ifodalashga intiladi. Masalan, yo‘l obrazi ko‘pincha inson hayotining ramzi sifatida talqin qilinadi. Bu obraz orqali insonning hayot yo‘li, uning izlanishlari va taqdiri tasvirlanadi. Shuningdek, tun obrazi insonning ichki kechinmalari yoki ruhiy holatini ifodalovchi ramz sifatida namoyon bo‘lishi mumkin. Aleksandr Faynberg poetikasida vaqt va yorug‘lik obrazlari ham muhim ramziy ma‘noga ega. Vaqt ko‘pincha inson hayotining o‘tkinchiligi, umrning qisqaligi kabi g‘oyalarni ifodalash uchun qo‘llanadi. Yorug‘lik obrazi esa ko‘pincha umid, ezgulik yoki ma‘naviy poklik ramzi sifatida talqin qilinadi. Bu obrazlar orqali shoir hayotning murakkabligi bilan bir qatorda, inson qalbidagi ezgulik va umid tuyg‘ularini ham ko‘rsatadi. Faynberg she‘riyatidagi ramzlar nafaqat badiiy bezak vazifasini bajaradi, balki chuqur falsafiy mazmunni ham ifodalaydi. Shoir ramziy obrazlar orqali inson hayoti, uning orzu-intilishlari va ruhiy izlanishlari haqida mushohada yuritadi. Natijada shoir lirikasida ramzlar tizimi yaxlit poetik struktura hosil qiladi. Bu tizim orqali o‘quvchi she‘r mazmunini chuqurroq anglash imkoniga ega bo‘ladi.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, Aleksandr Faynberg poetikasida ramziy obrazlar tizimi muhim badiiy xususiyatlardan biri hisoblanadi. Shoir ramzlardan foydalanish orqali o‘z asarlarining badiiy ta‘sirchanligini oshiradi va chuqur falsafiy mazmunni ifodalaydi. Faynberg she‘riyati ramziy obrazlar orqali inson hayoti, ruhiy kechinmalar va ma‘naviy qadriyatlarni badiiy jihatdan yoritib beradi. Shu sababli uning poetikasi zamonaviy she‘riyatda ramziy tafakkurning yorqin namunasidir.

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